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Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MEDiterraneanGrape**, **OLive** and **Durum** wheat food systems

Deliverable 6.24

Summary of Dissemination and Communication Activities n.4

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The MED-GOLD project aims to demonstrate the proof-of-concept on how climate services can make European agriculture and food systems more competitive, resilient and efficient by developing case studies for three hallmarks of the Mediterranean food system: grapes/wine, olives/olive oil and durum wheat/pasta.

This report describes and analyses the activities and strategies related to dissemination and communication which were performed and applied during the period M37-M54 (Nov 2020-May 2022). The main objective of these activities was to maximize the impact of the project through different channels and target audiences, as is described in MED-GOLD deliverable D7.1 “Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan” [RD.1].

This document is structured following those main topics:

- MED-GOLD website experience.
- Social Media Impact.
- Communication material (infosheets, infographic, video, Newsletter)
- Dissemination activities (Final showcasing 2022, Living Lab 2021, participatory workshops, webinars, publications, policy brief)
- External Communication channels
- Additional Dissemination channels. (Climate adapt, Zenodo)

1. OBJECTIVES

This document aims to provide a clear description of the activities performed during the last period (M37-M54) of MED-GOLD, mainly into the frame of the WP6 and in minor case WP5 [RD.3] remarking the parallel work made around each activity such as translation.

Although the content is similar to previous reports, an additional objective is to show the development during the project and identify the achievements by comparing the current results with the KPI initially defined.

Specific objectives:

- To collect and describe all the contributions and advances aimed at the dissemination of the MED-GOLD project.
- To present a report related to dissemination and communication activities performed by the consortium through the collection of data, reports, etc. that describe such activities.
- To analyse the behaviour of both social media and website through twitter analytics, google analytics.
- To ensure that all communication and dissemination activities have been properly logged, applying the procedure described in deliverable D7.1 “Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan [RD.1] and MED-GOLD Quality Plan [RD.2].

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the achievement of the following objectives (DOA, PartBTable1.1):

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot services with the wider European and global user communities for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	X

2. IMPACT

This document collects and analyses all the activities developed by WP6 during the last period (Nov 2020 – May 2022). In this sense, the outcomes will be used to evaluate the methodologies and strategies adopted to disseminate and communicate the project achievements. Considering the objective of this document, the impact is oriented to reach the public in general and the consortium members in particular who wish to define and apply a communication strategy following a similar procedure to MED-GOLD.

The fourth period continues with the process adopted and defined in D7.1, MED-GOLD Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan” [RD.1].

From a practical point of view, this period keeps the consolidated process achieved in the last period reported in D6.23 [RD.4].

No.	Expected impact	Yes
1	Providing added-value for the decision-making process addressed by the project, in terms of effectiveness, value creation, optimised opportunities and minimised risk	
2	Enhancing the potential for market uptake of climate services demonstrated by addressing the added value	
3	Ensuring the replicability of the methodological frameworks for value	

	added climate services in potential end-user markets	
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	X

3. DEFINITIONS

Concepts and terms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Concept / Term	Definition
Average Session Duration	Average Session Duration measures the average amount of time spent per session in the website. It is calculated by dividing total time spent across sessions by the total number of sessions.
Bounce Rate	Percentage of visitors that leave a webpage without taking an action, such as clicking on a link, filling out a form, or making a purchase.
New users	New users are users who have never been to your website, according to Google's tracking snippet; returning users have visited your site before.
Organic Search	Organic search is a source of traffic in <i>Google Analytics</i> ; one of the ways users get the website.
Users	Users are visitors who have initiated one session with your website or app within a specified period of time.

4. ACRONYMS

Acronyms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Acronym	Definition
CERN	European Council for Nuclear Research
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
EN	English
ES	Spanish
FR	French
GR	Greek (sometimes referenced as EL)
IT	Italian
KPI	key performance indicator
PT	Portuguese

5. REFERENCES

The following documents, although not part of this document, amplify or clarify its contents. Reference documents are those not applicable and referenced within this document. They are referenced in this document in the form [RD.x]:

Ref.	Title	Code	Version	Date
[RD.1]	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan	D7.1	2.1	30/05/2019
[RD.2]	MED-GOLD Quality Plan		1.3	23/04/2018
[RD.3]	MED-GOLD Grant Agreement			16/10/2017
[RD.4]	Summary of Dissemination and Communication Activities no.3	D6.23	1.2	30/11/2020

[RD.5]	Dissemination and Capacity Building Materials no.3	D6.16	2.0	15/11/2021
[RD.6]	Summary of Dissemination and Communication Activities no.2	D6.22	1.4	20/11/2019
[RD.7]	Build Your Author Platform: A Literary Agent's Guide to Growing Your Audience in 14 Steps			13/05/2014
[RD.8]	Compilation of Publications Abstracts n.3	D6.20	1.0	18/10/2021
[RD.9]	Climate Related Initiatives Interactions Report no.4	D6.13	1.3	24/11/2021
[RD.10]	Business Plan, Technology transfer and IPR report_v3	D6.10	3.1	31/03/2022
[RD.11]	Climate Service Replicability Report	D6.9	1.4	31/03/2022
[RD.12]	Report on the Summer training event no.2	D6.21	1.2	09/07/2021
[RD.13]	Data Management Plan	D7.2	2.0	29/05/2019
[RD.14]	Zenodo open data repository (CERN)". European University Institute. Retrieved 2022			05/04/2022
[RD.15]	Science-based knowledge relevant for Climate related Policies n.2	D6.17	1.2	10/11/2020
[RD.16]	Science-based knowledge relevant for Climate related Policies n.3	D6.18	1.2	27/11/2021

6. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

According to the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan the project's website (<https://www.med-gold.eu/>) and Twitter are the most important and effective channels to achieve the objective established in the project in terms of communication and dissemination.

The strategies adopted by MED-GOLD serve as a way to communicate activities, results and news related to the project. To reach the general public, policy makers, stakeholders, scientific and academic community, the consortium mainly used a multilanguage (6 languages: EN, ES, IT, PT, GR, FR) website and social media platforms (Twitter and YouTube) where multi-media materials were shared (videos, gifs, pictures, PDF documents). Additionally, the mailing list created from the beginning of the project and continuously updated was used to keep interested users informed about MED-GOLD and its advancements, including main results and activities. The preparation and publication of infosheets, infographics, policy briefs, scientific papers, publications in open access platforms, user guides, participatory workshops, living labs, webinars and the final showcase, among others, were included into the strategy to disseminate the project results, which is described in detail in the following sections.

6.1. STATE OF THE ART

In European research and innovation projects, the dissemination and communication of results is mandatory. According to article 38 of the grant agreement, the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner.

The Table 6-1 provides an overview of the communication and dissemination channels used during MED-GOLD.

Table 6-1 MED-GOLD Communication and dissemination channels

CHANNEL	ACTIVITY
MED-GOLD (Multilanguage) website	Communication
Twitter	Communication
YouTube	Communication and Dissemination
MED-GOLD Community database	Dissemination
MED-GOLD online forum	Dissemination
Newsletters, factsheets, news, report, press release	Dissemination
Training – Technical materials	Communication and Dissemination
Event participation	Communication and Dissemination
Workshops organization	Dissemination
Event Organization	Dissemination
Webinars	Dissemination
Scientific publications	Dissemination
Open Dataset	Dissemination

6.2. METHODS

The methods applied to complete this document used the following steps:

- Calculating increasing rates by comparing metrics such as website visits, website users, Twitter impressions, obtained in the previous reported period [RD.4] and current reported period.
- Compiling all results described on previous deliverables corresponding to (M37-M48)[RD.5][RD.8][RD.9]
- Compiling all activities through the email calls.
- Consulting WP6 meeting minutes.
- Direct measuring by consulting the spreadsheets available in the frame of WP6 (Paper list, MED-GOLD communication, dissemination and exploitation activities)
- Analysing the results of external tools such as Google Analytics, Twitter Analytics and Wayback Machine
- Indirect measuring through qualitative and quantitative estimation concluded from correlated or indirect information like number of visits, number of clicks, and traffic deviation, activity calls, etc.

6.3. COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES MAIN RESULTS

The work performed in the frame of communication activities are described and analyzed in detail in the following sections. In general terms, the project achieved its objectives such as production of materials, impact, and engagement of the target audiences, in which the quality of the results is remarkable. The results are summarized at the end of this document.

6.3.1. MED-GOLD WEBSITE

The multilanguage website did not undergo significant variations in its design. In this sense, the final design was published in January 2019, becoming in consolidated design with minor modifications since that moment (Figure 6-1).

Figure 6-1: MED-GOLD website design

The main effort was focused on updating the website and adding new content: homogenisation between different language versions, updating events, linking and publishing documents, updating the list of published papers, embedding videos, and creating a new tab dedicated to policy briefs.

After analysing the progress of the website using Wayback Machine it was identified that 69% of the work made on the website during the last two years was oriented to insert text/html (Figure 6-2). This includes the work made in the different multilanguage versions.

Figure 6-2: MED-GOLD website content update.

Remarkable updates in the different sections of the MED-GOLD website:

Publications: <https://www.med-gold.eu/documents-publications/>

- Scientific paper: in the 6 languages (keeping the original published language)
- MED-GOLD in the media: this update was made depending on the language in which the original publications was made.
- Infosheets in the 6 MED-GOLD languages

Policy Briefs: <https://www.med-gold.eu/documents-policy-briefs/>

- Add the final Policy Brief (Multilanguage)

Advisory Board: <https://www.med-gold.eu/advisory-board/>

- All Advisory Board members profile translated to all language versions

Event and News: <https://www.med-gold.eu/events-news/>

- Continuously updated section in all MED-GOLD languages

6.3.1.1. MULTILANGUAGE ACTIVITIES.

Multiple activities were developed by the translation teams with the objective to keep the homogeneity of all website multilanguage versions.

At the moment of writing this report, 17 activities focused on the translation of material are reported which are part (although not exclusively) of the website content. Figure 6-2 indicates the calls to translation activities in WP6. An extra effort was made for the French version, which had some delays with respect to the other languages during the last reported period [RD.4]. Currently the whole website is up to date.

Table 6-2 Multilanguage MED-GOLD Website Activities

Date	Activity	Material Translated	Number of Material / pages
05/04/2022	News	Website content	1
24/11/2021	Infosheet describing the MED-GOLD DASHBOARD for durum wheat sector users	Infosheet	1
06/09/2021	MED-GOLD climate services, ICT Platform, MED-GOLD Dashboard, Granodoro.net, MED-GOLD CASAS PDBM, MED-GOLD Climate Services	Infographic	6
26/07/2021	Web Update	Website content	1
29/06/2021	User Guide Granodoro.net	User guide	1
31/05/2021	Dashboard olive sector video	Video	1
18/05/2021	Survey Invitation	Survey – WP5	1
12/05/2021	Infosheet on the Dashboard for Olive Sector	Infosheet	1
04/05/2021	Assessing the benefits of the MED-GOLD Dashboard for SOGRAPE users	Website content	1
05/04/2021	Olivia Platform Infosheet, dashboard for wine, MED-GOLD contributes to the new EU Climate Adaptation Strategy	Infosheet / Website content	3
22/03/2021	Granodoro - Olivia Video subtitles' translation	Video	2
15/03/2021	Dashboard Video subtitles' translation	Video	1
03/03/2021	Durum Wheat Video	Video	1
23/02/2021	Grape Video, Olive Video, Meet our External Advisory Board - Mark Gishen	Video / Website content	3
01/02/2021	Meet our External Advisory Board - Andrew Paul Gutierrez, Meet our External Advisory Board - Angelo Riccaboni, Climate services visualisation: making the complex simple	Website content	3
15/12/2020	MED-GOLD General Assembly 2020, Living Lab 2020: The first training event from MED-GOLD to co-develop climate services for the agri-food sector, Climate adaptation in agriculture session hosted by MED-GOLD and VISCA	Website content	3
25/11/2020	Glossary	Website content	1

Into the frame of the communication strategy, some content of the social media channel Twitter has been translated to six languages.

6.3.1.2. GLOSSARY CONTENT ACTIVITIES

As continuation of the communication and dissemination strategies, the enrichment of the glossary was adopted after the second General Assembly (Oct-2019) [RD.4]. In this reported period, after the revision, discussion, scope of the definitions, revision, translation, final revision, publication. The final keywords were selected and categorized to achieve readable, understandable and compressible definitions in all languages.

The categorization and process applied in this activity is shown in the Table 6-3

Table 6-3 Glossary category according to readability

Category	Readiness Level
1	Ready to publish
2	REVIEW TRANSLATIONS - All translations are available but definitions have been revised. Translations need to be revised as well
3	TRANSLATION REQUIRED - New definition
4	ENGLISH VERSION NEEDS PROOFING WITH USERS
5	ENGLISH VERSION NEEDS REFINEMENT

The result of this process was 30 terms related to climate and climate services. (<https://www.med-gold.eu/glossary/>)

6.3.2. WEBSITE IMPACT AND USERS

The website was the core of the project Dissemination and Communication strategy, in this sense all metrics collected concerning to website help to identify the project’s impact. Although the majority of users were related to agriculture, climate, agri-food industry and academic, the objective was also to engage the general public.

In this section, an analysis focused on the website activity in terms of traffic helped to estimate the impact that will be presented using information provided by Google Analytics. Figure 6-3 compares the numbers of users who interacted with the MED-GOLD website on a monthly basis between November 2020 and April 2022 (M37 – M54) and the previous reported period (M25-M36). The figure shows that the number of visitors to the website had increased, particularly during special events (Living Lab 2021 and Final Showcase). The number of visitors during the second period (blue line) was always greater than the numbers in the previous period.

Figure 6-3: MED-GOLD website user activity.

Table 6.3 summarizes the most important aspects related to the MED-GOLD website audience, demonstrating the activities developed by the consortium have reached some of the objectives described in the previous reports.

Table 6-4 MED-GOLD website audience

Audience Activity	M37 - M54	M25 - M36	M13 - M24
Users	11528	3686	2785
New Users	11527	3632	2786
Sessions	15951	6613	4636
Page Views	32199	16101	11445
Bounce Rate	66.52%	61.18%	58.65%
Average Session Duration	00:01:42	0:02:43	0:02:32
Number of sessions per user	1.38	1.79	1.66
Pages/Session	2.02	2.43	2.47

The information collected from *Google Analytics* and summarized in Table 6-4 shows that the activity in the last period was higher than the two previously reported periods. Considering the total activity during the life

of the project, Figure 6-4 shows the improvement in the contribution of users, new users, sessions and page views during the reported period, while the rest of the indicators had a similar behaviour to previous periods.

Figure 6-4: MED-GOLD website comparison by periods.

The MED-GOLD project is focused on the three hallmarks of the agri-food Mediterranean sector. In this sense, the analysis of the users indicates the majority reside in the Mediterranean region, identified in *Google Analytics* as southern Europe. Users from this region provided the best figures considering the Average session, pages and timing interactions. This relation suggests the quality of the experience was higher when compared with users from other regions, especially Southeast Asia where the users increased the number of visits but the average session time is lower (Table 6-5).

Table 6-5 MED-GOLD website users by regions

Region	Users	New Users	Sessions	Bounce Rate	Pages/Session	Avg. Session Duration
Southern Europe	3569	3561	7128	52.99%	2.76	191.74
Southeast Asia	3122	3135	3148	95.71%	1.04	0.42
Northern America	1153	1162	1223	84.55%	1.27	13.95
Western Europe	1087	1078	1341	68.31%	1.82	63.43
Eastern Asia	650	667	704	73.01%	1.31	10.58
Northern Europe	562	558	738	67.62%	1.82	66.77
Southern Asia	265	275	332	54.52%	1.60	51.07
South America	255	268	348	50.00%	1.85	92.46
Northern Africa	205	214	260	59.62%	1.81	71.14
Western Asia	158	160	196	47.45%	2.14	110.40

*Regions in bold represents the higher quality interactions. User and New User (see definitions table)

The general activity by countries was increased, however special focus on the Mediterranean countries (Figure 6-5) indicates the importance of the stakeholder's location as well as the precedence of the majority of partners (Table 6-5)

Figure 6-5: MED-GOLD website user in the Mediterranean countries.

The *Bounce Rate* indicates that users in the Mediterranean Region, South America and Western Asia had the most balanced interactions. Additionally, the *Average Session Duration* allowed to select countries where the interactions were good in terms of quality. The results reinforce the higher weight of countries from partners participating in the MED-GOLD consortium (Table 6-6)

Table 6-6 MED-GOLD website users by countries

Country	Users	New Users	Sessions	Bounce Rate	Pages/Session	Avg. Session Duration
Italy	1578	1564	3265	52.96%	2.56	183.71
Spain	925	927	2154	46.84%	3.41	261.29
Portugal	561	560	1043	58.29%	2.54	136.46
Greece	428	427	563	67.14%	2.02	95.66
France	334	330	421	62.95%	1.93	78.71
United Kingdom	242	238	397	56.17%	2.26	113.19
Germany	165	163	232	56.90%	2.02	53.48
Tunisia	112	112	137	62.77%	2.09	102.64
Belgium	109	105	158	62.03%	2.30	118.85
Colombia	59	60	68	75.00%	1.28	53.88
Turkey	45	46	58	44.83%	1.97	107.33
Argentina	31	34	39	48.72%	2.00	107.97
Australia	31	31	66	72.73%	1.53	76.24
Bosnia & Herzegovina	26	26	30	73.33%	1.40	110.93
Chile	26	26	35	42.86%	2.34	79.37
Ireland	26	26	28	64.29%	1.93	64.18
Egypt	23	25	29	37.93%	1.62	51.24

*Countries in bold are part of MED-GOLD consortium.

The multilanguage website had a positive impact in terms of participation as is demonstrated by the *google* report (Table 6-7). In general, translation activities supported by the consortium had a good impact considering the number of visitors in PT, GR, ES and IT.

Table 6-7 MED-GOLD website visitors by language

Language	Users	New Users	Sessions	Bounce Rate	Pages/Session	Avg. Session Duration
en	6555	6589	7895	67.52%	1.99	87.19
it-it	1152	1142	2041	56.74%	2.38	157.91
es-es	687	686	1475	50.31%	3.11	250.51
en-gb	675	691	1119	42.27%	2.24	121.54
pt-pt	436	435	867	59.17%	2.50	131.69
fr-fr	273	279	360	63.89%	1.98	97.58
lt	261	260	412	54.37%	2.34	151.05
el-gr	228	228	267	73.78%	1.76	88.22

Considering the default channel grouping, the acquisition of users by *direct search* was 7739, by *Organic Search* was 3083, by referral 701, by social media 455, by email 3 and other 1. With these figures, it can be concluded that social and referral are the most effective ways to redirect traffic to the website. Although the organic search is relevant, this figure is not accurate because it was not possible to establish the keywords used by 2698 users; the rest of 385 users were redirected by using keywords like "wine studies", "olive" or "776467 med-gold".

Once the different reports provided by *Google Analytics* had been analysed, it can be concluded that the activities developed by the consortium during this reporting period had a positive result in terms of impact measured by users, new users and page/sessions.

6.3.3.MED-GOLD SOCIAL NETWORKS

Twitter was the main social media channel selected by the consortium to communicate and disseminate the project as it was defined in the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan [RD.1]. YouTube was also used as a way to share the different videos recorded and created during the project. According to Twitter Analytics (Table 6-8), the activity during the final reporting period was higher than the previous period [RD.4]

Table 6-8 MED-GOLD Twitter results

Result	Present Period M37 - M54	Previous Period M24-M36
Tweets published	278	157
impressions	137393	101545
engagements	3348	1650
engagement rate	7.5	3.5
retweets	675	279
replies	18	8
likes	893	423
user profile clicks	271	120
url clicks	404	353
hashtag clicks	36	10
detail expands	514	229
Media views	1631	220
Media engagements	536	219

These numbers indicate that activities had good results, which relied on the ability to define the right moment to post and the translation of key posts to other languages. The periods with higher impressions and engagements (Figure 6-6) were those related to MED-GOLD events (LivingLab 2021, multilanguage participatory workshops, final showcase 2022). Making use of ancillary material (gif, videos, pictures, pdf) and selecting key hashtags was also useful (Figure 6-7).

Figure 6-6: Monthly MED-GOLD Twitter Performance – Impressions (upper) Engagements (lower)

Although the current number of followers (520) were not as high as the project expected [RD.1], the consortium strategy was focused on the profile of the followers and maintaining their interest, instead of achieving a large number of followers with low interest in the project. Such a result is reflected in the number of attendees in the MED-GOLD final showcase explained below. Following the guidelines described in the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan [RD.1] the majority of tweets are simple, direct, contain relevant information and include hashtags. In the majority of cases the posting times selected were 09:00, 12:00, 15:00 and 19:00 according to Jelen and McCallister [RD.7]

Figure 6-7: MED-GOLD Twitter screenshot

As was mentioned in the previous report [RD.4], MED-GOLD adopted *Buffer* (bufferapp.com) to post material in an organized way. The methodology applied was in the case that it was necessary to prepare the tweets, request translation by the translation team and then schedule the posting time.

The [YouTube channel](#) (Figure 6-8) has a double function, first to store the videos produced by the consortium and secondly to broadcast the most relevant activities such as events, promotions and tutorials. Regarding the information collected from Youtube, the MED-GOLD channel has 2869 visualizations, and it contains 38 videos to date.

Figure 6-8: MED-GOLD YouTube Channel

6.3.4. MED-GOLD MAILING LISTS

The mailing list was created throughout the project through the collection of information from European and national organizations [RD.6]. Currently the list obtained of contacts registered in the MED-GOLD community has around 290 members from different countries. The WP6 translation team supported the translation of the letters sent through the mailing list to engage participants in the different MED-GOLD events.

Figure 6-9: MED-GOLD Community Contact List by Language

The events organized during this period allowed to increase the size of the MED-GOLD contacts database. Comparing the available information, the number of registered attendees is higher compared with the number of contacts reported in D6.23 [RD.4] (170): Living Lab 2021 (20 new Contacts), Participatory Workshops (98 new registers after Nov 2020), MED-GOLD final Showcase (240 from pre-registered attendees). In addition, the interaction with other initiatives provided new contacts who were added to the mailing list.

6.3.5. MED-GOLD NEWSLETTERS

The Newsletters were a mechanism to keep the MED-GOLD community and the general public informed about the results, events, and advances in the project. This communication material [RD.5] was shared through the [MED-GOLD website](#), Twitter account and project mailing list.

During this reported period the [Newsletter N°5](#) (Dec 2020), [Newsletter N°6](#) (Jun 2021) and [Newsletter N°7](#) (Dec 2021) were released. The Newsletter N°8 is being prepared at the moment and will be sent to the MED-GOLD community at the very end of the project, as a farewell and with a summary of the last achievements.

The most notable topics in Newsletter 5 were “Finishing the testing of MED-GOLD climate services tools” and announcements about Living Lab 2021, New video: Use cases on the application of the MED-GOLD Dashboard, Info sheet: Climate predictions for agriculture. The Newsletter 6 highlighted that MED-GOLD was acknowledged by the European Commission as one of the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation contributors who helped to shape the EU Climate Adaptation Strategy, which was adopted in March 2021. Finally, Newsletter 7 remarked on the MED-GOLD activities focused on showcasing the MED-GOLD dashboard through several participatory workshops.

According to *Twitter Analytics*, the announcement of Newsletter 5 had 431 impressions and the Newsletter 6 announcement had 683 impressions. Google Analytics (Table 6-9) indicated that the Newsletter page had 1016 views considering all languages.

Table 6-9 MED-GOLD Newsletter views

Page	Views	Unique Views
/media/	638	414
/it/media-it/	179	121
/es/media-3/	105	78
/pt/media-2/	64	39

/fr/media-fr/	30	21
Total	1016	673

6.3.6.EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

The participation of partners has also contributed to the communication of MED-GOLD using their own communication channels and strategies. During this reported period, 135 “external activities” related to communication were collected from the MED-GOLD partners. A special mention is the use of *Climate Adapt Newsletter* to circulate the invitation to Participatory Workshops and the Final Showcase as well as the mention of MED-GOLD in the Publication Office of the EU (Figure 6-11)

Figure 6-10: MED-GOLD Communication Activity

In the MED-GOLD website are available some appearances of the project in other media (Table 6-10).

Table 6-10 MED-GOLD in Media

Type	Web Version	Number
Interview	EN	3
Press release	EN	5
About MED-GOLD	IT	7
Interview	IT	2
Podcast	IT	1
Video	IT	1
About MED-GOLD	ES	7
Video	ES	1
News	ES	1

About MED-GOLD	PT	7
Press release	PT	1

Figure 6-11: MED-GOLD External Communication appearances

6.4. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES MAIN RESULTS

The activities concerning Dissemination also had good results and increased when compared to the last reported period. This increase was mainly due to the adoption of videos showcasing the MED-GOLD dashboard applicability in the three sectors, multiple participatory workshops, participation in different events and publications.

6.4.1. MED-GOLD EVENTS

Among the dissemination activities, this report distinguishes between participation in events and organized events. The first has as main objective to bring the work made and the results to the largest audience possible beyond the MED-GOLD environment, meanwhile the second are more focused in the MED-GOLD community, in some cases increased by the interaction with the firsts.

During this reported period, MED-GOLD participated in fourteen relevant events. The majority of the presentations were oral and delivered remotely [RD.5].

Table 6-11 MED-GOLD Events Participation

Event	Location	Date	Presentation type
Final event of the VISCA project, Presentation of the MED-GOLD project	online	15 Dec 2020	Oral
Second national CLIMALERT workshop, Water and vineyards: limits of planning and possible solutions	online	5 Mar 2021	Oral

European Geosciences Union General Assembly, various presentations at the session about Climate services – underpinning science,	online	19-30 Apr 2021	Oral
Andalusian Government webinar, Models for the prediction of the olive fruit fly and prays	online	22 Apr 2021	Oral
C3S Conference and General Assembly, MED-GOLD as an example of project for climate resilience	online	18-20 May 2021	Oral
Met Office Climate Science Conference, Poster showing elements of the MED-GOLD dashboard	online	11-12 May 2021	Poster
SECLI-FIRM stakeholder workshop, Presentation of the MED-GOLD dashboard as a case study for agriculture	online	25 May 2021	Oral
European Meteorological Society annual meeting, Understanding climate and non-climate decision triggers to minimize Spring rainfall risks in vineyards	online	6-10 Sep 2021	Oral
SPIE Remote Sensing for Agriculture, Ecosystems, and Hydrology XXIII conference, Satellite imagery and climate variables suggest variations in the phenology of olive groves in Southern Spain	online	13-18 Sep 2021	Poster
Expoliva fair 2021	Jaén, Spain	21-25 Sep 2021	Dissemination materials in booth
Smart Agrifood Summit	Málaga, Spain	30 Sep - 1 Oct 2021	Dissemination materials in booth
International Organisation of Vine and Wine (OIV) expert group meeting, Presentation of the MED- GOLD dashboard	online	15 Oct 2021	Oral
C3S and MedECC workshop 'Data for climate action in the Mediterranean, Presentation of the MED- GOLD project	online	25 Oct 2021	Oral
Copa-Cogeca meeting of the Working Party on Olives & Olive Oil, Presentation of the MED-GOLD dashboard	online	18 Nov 2021	Oral
VIII Congress of Agro-food Cooperatives of Spain	Toledo Spain	30 Jun-1 Jul 2022	Poster

The sectorial participatory workshops were key to the dissemination activities. This task was developed in WP5 and had as the main objective showing the advances of the MED-GOLD dashboard, to collect information about the perception of the end-user and evaluate the MED-GOLD climate services. The information collected was used to detect the users' needs as part of the MED-GOLD Business plan [RD.10]. The methodology was used to collect information in the Climate Services Replicability Report [RD.11]. In addition, during the MED-GOLD Final showcase event, two webinars were presented. Finally, the MED-GOLD Living Lab was presented in 2021. Table 6-12 summary the events organized by MED-GOLD

Table 6-12 MED-GOLD Events

Event	Workshop	Type	Registered	Attended	Date	Engage rate
1	MED-GOLD Final Showcase	Conference	185	167	Mar 29 - 30, 2022	90%
2	Discover how to apply the MED-GOLD climate services to different sectors	Webinar	28	71	Mar 29, 2022	254%
3	Coproduction of climate services: success stories from MED-GOLD	Webinar	25	87	Mar 29, 2022	348%
4	MED-GOLD participatory workshop on the climate service for the olive oil, wine, and durum wheat sectors (in English and Greek)	Workshop	63	19	Mar 1, 2022	30%
5	MED-GOLD participatory workshop on the climate service for the olive and olive oil sector (in Italian)	Workshop	22	7	Feb 22, 2022	32%
6	MED-GOLD & MEDCLIV participatory workshop on the climate service for the wine sector (in Italian)	Workshop	50	14	Feb 15, 2022	28%

7	MED-GOLD participatory workshop on the climate service for the wine sector (in Portuguese)	Workshop	77	22	Feb 2, 2022	29%
8	MED-GOLD participatory workshop on the climate service for the olive and olive oil sector (in English)	Workshop	16	6	Jan 17, 2022	38%
9	MED-GOLD participatory workshop on the climate service for the wine sector (in English)	Workshop	25	12	Dec 13, 2021	48%
10	MED-GOLD participatory workshop on the climate service for the olive and olive oil sector (in Spanish)	Workshop	20	6	Dec 9, 2021	30%
11	MED-GOLD participatory workshop on the climate service for the durum wheat (in Italian)	Workshop	12	12	Feb 2, 2022	100%
12	MED-GOLD Living Lab 2021	School	22	16	May 27- Jun 24, 2021	73%

* The events in bold will be described in the sections below. The information of participatory workshops corresponds to active participation. This measure was collected by *Mentimeter* (<https://www.mentimeter.com/app>) used during each activity.

The global data allow to establish that rate of successful (attendees / registered) is 80%. The participation by countries and gender are shows in the Figure 6-12. As expecting, the most active countries are located in the Mediterranean Region. The interaction with other initiatives and the work made in the context of replicability also was reflected with the participation of Colombia, Tunisian and Lebanon.

Figure 6-12: MED-GOLD events participants by gender and countries.

6.4.2.INTERACTION WITH OTHER INITIATIVES

The interactions with initiatives similar to MED-GOLD are a dissemination way as well as a valuable information source fundamental to identify other user needs, new approaches, markets, potential replicability, etc. Based on the results of the last Climate Related Initiatives Interactions Report [RD.9], the MED-GOLD partners are involved in many other projects involving the provision of climate services and Agriculture. From May 2020 to current, the active interactions with Climate Services projects are 10 and with Agriculture projects are 11. The possible detected new interactions are:

- AfriCultuRes.
- BLUE-ACTION (Arctic impact on weather and climate)
- CAFÉ (Climate Advanced Forecasting of sub-seasonal extremes)
- CLIMAGRI
- Climate-ADAPT
- ISIPedia
- MEDCLIV (Mediterranean Climate Vine & Wine Ecosystem)
- AgMIP (Agricultural Model Intercomparison and Improvement Project)
- Cenicafé
- Global Agriculture Sectoral Information System
- MedECC (Mediterranean Experts on Climate and environmental Change)
- SUSTAIN OLIVE
- VitiGEOSS (Vineyard Innovative Tool based on the InteGration of Earth Observation Services and in-field Sensors)

At the moment to elaborate this report, some of those potential interactions were materialized in some of the activities of other initiatives (events, workshops or webinars). For example, AfriCultuRes participated with a replicability use case in the final showcase whereas communication materials from the VitiGEOSS project were showcased in the event's virtual booths. On the other hand, MEDCLIV participated in the participatory workshop dedicated to wine. In addition, MED-GOLD published some of the events in the Climate-ADAPT news portal. Portal.

6.4.3.MED-GOLD LIVING LAB 2021

This [Living Lab](#) was the second version of the MED-GOLD summer school adapted to the Covid-19 pandemic. This event was divided into nine sessions (five plenary and four hands-on sessions) over five weeks. The periodic activities were delivered by speakers across different disciplines relevant to the development and implementation of climate services for the agriculture sector, including climate modelling, agriculture and user engagement. According with the information collected by the organizing team [RD.12], the number of registered students was 22 and a total of 16 actually participated (11 female and 5 male). A complete summary and feedback is available here: [LivingLab2021](#)

Figure 6-13: MED-GOLD Living Lab participation.

The different sessions of the Living Lab 2021 are available in the [MED-GOLD YouTube](#) and count with 210 visualisations considering all sessions. Meanwhile *Google analytics* indicated that the Living Lab 2021 event counted with 1447 views (653 en-version, 401 the Common background, 202 it-version, 135 es-version, 30 pt-version, 14 fr-version, 12 gr-version)

Figure 6-14: MED-GOLD Living Lab screenshot

6.4.4. MED-GOLD INFOSHEET

Five [infosheets](#) were published during this period, meaning a total of eleven infosheets since the MED-GOLD project started. The most recent infosheets were:

- MED-GOLD dashboard for wine sector users
- MED-GOLD dashboard for olive sector users
- MED-GOLD dashboard for durum wheat sector users
- Olivia platform for olive sector users
- Granoduro.net platform for durum wheat sector users

Figure 6-15: MED-GOLD latest Infosheets

According to google analytics, the publications section received 1202 views during this period.

6.4.5. MED-GOLD INFOGRAPHICS

Six [infographics](#) were published and translated to six languages during this period. The objective is easily to describe how the MED-GOLD climate Services works and is related with other tools.

- Developing climate services for European agriculture and food systems
- MED-GOLD ICT PLATFORM
- MED-GOLD dashboard
- Granoduro.net
- MED-GOLD CASAS PDBM
- MED-GOLD platform ecosystem

6.4.6. MED-GOLD WEBINAR

As was mentioned in the chapter dedicated to MED-GOLD events, two webinars took place during the MED-GOLD Final Showcase.

- Discover how to apply the MED-GOLD climate services to different sectors (March 29 2022). Four parallel sessions were focused on a different food system covered in MED-GOLD. The MED-GOLD climate services tool was briefly showcased, and the audience was encouraged to engage in an interactive discussion with the speakers. Total Attendees: 82.
- Coproduction of climate services: success stories from MED-GOLD (March 29 2022): This session focused on the technical aspects of the co-development process of climate services and delivering useful and usable information, as well as on evaluating the value brought to users. Total attendees: 87

6.4.7. MED-GOLD DISSEMINATION (ZENODO)

Following the MED-GOLD Data Management Plan [RD.13] and the directives for the H2020 projects: “an open access to data, documents, deliverables, scientific reports and publications in peer reviewed journals represents the fundamental leverage to provide and produce direct and indirect benefits of the H2020 Research program on society” [RD.14]. The consortium have used Zenodo as a way to openly share the

material produced by MED-GOLD (Figure 6-16). Zenodo is a multi-disciplinary open repository maintained by CERN. This platform is presented as a place of dissemination, being a widely used medium throughout the world. In this sense, the MED-GOLD partners have uploaded some of the material produced in the frame of the project. Currently, there are 37 files associated with MED-GOLD, of which 24 were uploaded during the reporting period.

Figure 6-16: MED-GOLD in Zenodo

6.4.8. MED-GOLD FORUM

The MED-GOLD forum is oriented mainly to keep contact with the MED-GOLD community and discuss open topics such as the results of events like webinars, schools, workshops, etc. During this reporting period, the activity in the forum was low mainly because there were no new topics.

6.4.9. MED-GOLD PUBLICATIONS

After September 2020 the number of abstracts submitted was 23 according to D6.20 [RD.8], however at the moment to write this document a new abstract was accepted and published increasing this number to 24; 10 more than reported in the D6.23 [RD.4]. In addition, the consortium is preparing publications for the special issue in the Climate Services journal to be submitted by 31 July 2022.

The percentage of submitted abstracts by sector is showed in the Figure 6-17:

Figure 6-17: Abstracts submitted by thematic

Currently there are 20 papers published and available in the MED-GOLD website (Table 6-13):

Table 6-13 MED-GOLD Papers

No	Title	Citation	Year
1	Simulating the effect of El Niño Southern Oscillation on the worldwide wheat prices	Giuseppe, Edmondo Di and Giulioni, Gianfranco and Pasqui, Massimiliano. Simulating the effect of El Niño Southern Oscillation on the worldwide wheat prices. International Journal of Computational Economics and Econometrics, V12. N°1-2. 2022	2022
2	Multi-annual prediction of drought and heat stress to support decision making in the wheat sector	Solaraju-Murali, B., Gonzalez-Reviriego, N., Caron, LP. et al. Multi-annual prediction of drought and heat stress to support decision making in the wheat sector. npj Clim Atmos Sci 4, 34 (2021).	2021
3	Biological invasion risk assessment of Tuta absoluta: mechanistic versus correlative methods	Ponti, L., Gutierrez, A.P., de Campos, M.R. et al. Biological invasion risk assessment of Tuta absoluta: mechanistic versus correlative methods. Biol Invasions 23, 3809–3829 (2021).	2021
4	Engagement, involvement and empowerment: Three realms of a coproduction framework for climate services	Dragana Bojovic, Asuncion Lera St. Clair, Isadora Christel, Marta Terrado, Philipp Stanzel, Paula Gonzalez, Erika J. Palin, Engagement, involvement and empowerment: Three realms of a coproduction framework for climate services, Global Environmental Change, Volume 68, 2021, 102271, ISSN 0959-3780,	2021
5	Invasive potential of tropical fruit flies in temperate regions under climate change	Gutierrez, A.P., Ponti, L., Neteler, M. et al. Invasive potential of tropical fruit flies in temperate regions under climate change. Commun Biol 4, 1141 (2021).	2021
6	Global loss of climatically suitable areas for durum wheat growth in the future	Andrej Ceglár ^{3,1} , Andrea Toreti ¹ , Matteo Zampieri ¹ and Conxita Royo ² . Published 19 October 2021. 2021 The Author(s). Published by IOP Publishing Ltd Environmental Research Letters, Volume 16, Number 10	2021
7	Impact of low temperature and host plant on Tuta absoluta	Campos, M.R., Amiens-Desneux, E., Béarez, P., Soares, A., Ponti, L., Biondi, A., Harwood, J.D. and Desneux, . (2021), Impact of low temperature and host plant on Tuta absoluta. Entomol Exp Appl, 169: 984-996.	2021
8	Intercepted photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) and spatial and temporal distribution of transmitted par under high-density and super high-density olive orchards.	Rosati, A.; Marchionni, D.; Mantovani, D.; Ponti, L.; Famiani, F. Intercepted Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) and Spatial and Temporal Distribution of Transmitted PAR under High-Density and Super High-Density Olive Orchards. Agriculture 2021, 11, 351.	2021
9	Seasonal climate forecast can inform the European agricultural sector well in advance of harvesting	Ceglár, A., Toreti, A. Seasonal climate forecast can inform the European agricultural sector well in advance of harvesting. npj Clim Atmos Sci 4, 42 (2021).	2021
10	Satellite imagery and climate variables suggest variations in the phenology of olive groves in Southern Spain	A. Fernandez-Carrillo, F. W. Rivas-Gonzalez, B. Revilla-Romero, "Satellite imagery and climate variables suggest variations in the phenology of olive groves in Southern Spain," Proc. SPIE 11856, Remote Sensing for Agriculture, Ecosystems, and Hydrology XXIII, 118560M (12 September 2021)	2021
11	Unprecedented rainfall in northern Portugal	Sanderson, M. G., Teixeira, M., Fontes, N., Silva, S., Graça, A. (2021) Unprecedented rainfall in northern Portugal. International Viticulture and Enology Society (IVES).	2021
12	Estimating resilience of crop production systems: From theory to practice	Matteo Zampieri, Christof J. Weissteiner, Bruna Grizzetti, Andrea Toreti, Maurits van den Berg, Frank Dentener. Science of The Total Environment, Volume 735, 2020, 139378, ISSN 0048-9697. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.139378 .	2020

No	Title	Citation	Year
13	Clisagri: An R package for agro-climate services	Ceglar, A., Toreti, A., Zampieri, M., Manstretta, V., Bettati, T., & Bratu, M. (2020). <i>Climate Services</i> , 20, 100197.	2020
14	The Influence of Climate on Agricultural Decisions for Three European Crops: A Systematic Review	Mihailescu, E., & Soares, M. B. (2020). <i>Front. Sustain. Food Syst.</i> , https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2020.00064 .	2020
15	The coffee agroecosystem: bio-economic analysis of coffee berry borer control (<i>Hypothenemus hampei</i>).	Cure, J.R., Rodríguez, D., Gutierrez, A.P. et al. The coffee agroecosystem: bio-economic analysis of coffee berry borer control (<i>Hypothenemus hampei</i>). <i>Sci Rep</i> 10, 12262 (2020). https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-68989-x	2020
16	Time-varying impact of climate on maize and wheat yields in France since 1900	Andrej Ceglar et al 2020 <i>Environ. Res. Lett.</i> 15 094039	2020
17	Multi-year prediction of European summer drought conditions for the agricultural sector	Solaraju-Murali, B., Caron, L. P., Gonzalez-Reviriego, N., & Doblaz-Reyes, F. J. (2019). <i>Environmental Research Letters</i> , 14(12), 124014.	2019
18	A Counting Process Approach for Trend Assessment of Drought Condition	Di Giuseppe, E., Pasqui, M., Magno, R., & Quaresima, S. (2019). <i>Hydrology</i> , 6(4), 84.	2019
19	A Novel Computational Model of the Wheat Global Market with an Application to the 2010 Russian Federation Case	Giulioni, G., Di Giuseppe, E., Toscano, P., Miglietta, F., & Pasqui, M. (2019). <i>Journal of Artificial Societies & Social Simulation</i> , 22(3).	
20	Analysis of Grape Production in the Face of Climate Change	Ponti, L., Gutierrez, A., Boggia, A., & Neteler, M. (2018). <i>Climate</i> , 6(2), 20.	2018

6.4.10. CONTACT WITH THE POLICY COMMUNITY

The continuing interaction with the policy community is a relevant process considering that MED-GOLD aims to support policy making [RD.15][RD.16].

- The MED-GOLD team supported the European Commission, EASME Executive Agency, and the Climateurope Team to organize the workshop '*Climate services for a climate-resilient Europe - Climate services for a climate-resilient Europe Success stories, lessons learnt and remaining challenges*' scheduled for 2 December 2020. In this event, the MED-GOLD and VISCA projects hosted the session "*How can climate services support adaptation to climate change in agriculture?*"
- MED-GOLD contributed to the draft of the sustainable food Farm to Fork strategy: "*IMPORTANCE TO CONSIDER THE ROLE OF CLIMATE SERVICES IN FRAMING THE FARM TO FORK STRATEGY*" on 20 March, 2020
- MED-GOLD released the [Policy Brief](#) (multilanguage) Sectoral Indicators to Support The Climate Policy Brief: "*Sectoral Climate Services For A Sustainable Adaptation in agriculture*" (Figure 6-18).
- Videos (multi-language subtitled). As part of the activities of C&D described in the previous sections several videos were recorded. Aware of the importance to engage the policy-making audience some of them were focused on include a clear message, highlighting the needs in the adoption of Climate Services.[RD.6][RD.16]: [MED-GOLD dashboard](#) , [dashboard for the Olive sector](#), [Olivia Platform for the Olive sector](#), [granoduro.net decision support tool](#).

Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional MEDiterranean Grape, Olive and Durum wheat food systems

Grant Agreement n° 776467

- MED-GOLD has developed, implemented and tested co-designed climate services to support sustainable adaptation in agriculture.
- MED-GOLD services address the needs of a broad range of end users, from farmers to regional, national, and European stakeholders.
- MED-GOLD services contribute to enhance climate resilience and offer tools to address the climate resilience of the new Common Agricultural Policy.
- MED-GOLD has an essential role in achieving the targets set by the Green Deal, the Farm to Fork Strategy, and the forthcoming Climate Law.

The socio-economic challenges posed by climate change require actions and tools for a dynamic, sustainable adaptation contributing to the 2030 mitigation targets and the 2030 sustainable development goals. In this context, sectoral climate services play a key role by offering tailored climate information. An effective climate service supports decision-makers and actions to adapt, reduce the risks, increase resilience, and whenever possible it turns climate change into an opportunity. An effective climate service covers different time scales, from the coming weeks to the coming decades, and addresses the needs of different users acting at the local, national, and regional levels. However, such a climate service did not exist five years ago and the EU-H2020 MED-GOLD project was financed to contribute to fill the gap and develop prototypes for the agricultural sector. MED-GOLD focused on three key agricultural sectors (olive-wine, grape, and olive production) and focused on the Mediterranean region. However, all its pilot services have been developed by ensuring broader applicability to other regions and other sectors. The limiting risks and enabling factors to a broader consistency of end-users (farmers, breeders, regional stakeholders, food companies). MED-GOLD has achieved its challenging goals.

Informed from the very beginning in the design of the services, end-users contributed to defining the specific needs, followed the development of the services by providing continuous feedback, and tested their effectiveness and usability. Each pilot service was co-developed with specific users and with a specific technical team in MED-GOLD by adopting a common

methodological approach across the three climate service pilots. Thanks to this co-design approach, the MED-GOLD services address the needs (by providing targeted climate information) of farmers, breeders, regional stakeholders, and national and European policymakers.

MED-GOLD services build on and take advantage of existing initiatives as well as data and infrastructure facilities. The Common Climate Data Store represents a cornerstone of climate services and has offered the possibility to transform existing data into sectoral information through the development and the implementation of a dedicated platform and open-source tools that are freely available. This approach made possible the integration of MED-GOLD services into existing decision-supporting systems already in use by hundreds of farms.

The tool developed contributes to decision-making during the agricultural season, as well as to its long-term planning. They provide crop-specific information regarding optimal agronomic decisions and actions from sowing to harvest. A dynamic, continuous flow of information is generated by integrating observations, as long as they are made available, with seasonal predictions reaching users at any point in the crop season. Crop-specific climate risks deriving from unfavorable conditions and/or extreme events (e.g. drought, heat stress at flowering) are notified at any scale of the information provided to offer farmers the possibility to act and minimize the

Figure 17: Schematic representation of MED-GOLD

Figure 18: MED-GOLD Policy Brief

Impact. MED-GOLD services do not only aim to get higher and more stable crop yields but also to grow crops sustainably. Key decisions on fertilization rate, timing, and the number of applications are supported by the information offered. Such support will be crucial to successfully initiate and complete the transition to a sustainable food system as foreseen by the Farm to Fork strategy, e.g. to reduce by 20% the use of fertilizers by 2030. MED-GOLD services also contribute to enhancing the climate performance and resilience of farms, that addressing the climate ambition of the new Common Agricultural Policy. The services also represent concrete tools that may be used by the Member States to offer voluntary for farmers (climate and agro-environmental schemes in their Strategic Plans). The co-developed services also support long-term investments (e.g. on infrastructure) to cope with and adapt to climate change, to assist farmers in maintaining their socio-economic well-being and contribution to European competitiveness.

MED-GOLD services support breeders in assessing future climate risks, by providing projected conditions under which crop genotypes will be exposed and, thus, identifying optimal ones. The services can be also used to test a broad range of ideotypes, testing different key traits, to better orient current breeding programmes. Looking at the longer time scales, covering the next decades, MED-GOLD offers crop specific evaluation of climate suitability by applying innovative machine learning approaches. Information on changes in suitability support regional, national, and European stakeholders in early planning and in diversifying adequately policy measures to counteract the impacts of climate change, balance the internal market, and in some cases act on widening the entire supply chain. The offered services on prepared crop yield, under different assumptions, and scenarios, complements the support to all levels of stakeholders. The tools developed can also support the European Commission's agricultural activities, such as the short

and medium-term agricultural outlook. For instance, part of the MED-GOLD durum wheat prototype has been already implemented into the crop yield monitoring and forecasting system of the European Commission Joint Research Centre in support of the short-term agricultural outlook.

The changing climate poses challenges in the decision-making process of olive growers and olive oil producers that also need to select their irrigation, fertilization and pesticide application strategies. It also modifies the occurrence of crop diseases, along with their potential damage, and can favour the development of new pests. Thus, integrating state-of-the-art conditions is key for the adaptation of the olive sector and climate services can help in this process. Furthermore, for olive producers the changing climate poses new challenges such as in defining long-term strategies, and in viticulture, vineyard and stock management. Climate services, particularly predictions of climate variables and bioclimatic indices, can help in these decisions.

To these goals, MED-GOLD creates a visualization tool, the dashboard, which provides easy-to-use access to information on past climate and predictions of future climate at different time scales. The tool has been co-developed with users to ensure that it addresses their needs and expectations. Anyone can access the dashboard via the MED-GOLD website, or by installing the MED-GOLD desktop application.

The unique tool that has been created (connecting scientists, practitioners, farmers, stakeholders, and food companies) within MED-GOLD opens the way to the future strategies that will be needed to address the challenges posed by climate change: smart food health, stability, sustainability, and competitiveness. The project has demonstrated the benefits of involving all key actors of the food systems in building services for a climate resilient and sustainable agricultural sector. These services will be essential to reach the targets set by the Green Deal and the forthcoming Climate Law while contributing to the 2030 sustainable Development Goals.

Figure 2: The co-developing MED-GOLD pilot services approach scheme

Figure 18: MED-GOLD Policy Brief

Participation in International initiatives:

- ECCA 2021 - CLIMATE ADAPTATION SOLUTIONS (May to June, 2021,)
- MACSUR SCIPOL KF - SCIENCE-POLICY KNOWLEDGE FORUM ITALY (Oct 2021)
- THE MED-GOLD DASHBOARD, SHOWCASED AT EXPERTS OF THE INTERNATIONAL ORGANISATION OF VINE AND WINE (Oct 2021)

The MED-GOLD Final Event (2022) counted with speakers from important international organizations: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), International Olive Council (IOC), European Commission Experts, European Centre for Development Policy Management, Copernicus Climate Change Service, International Organisation of Vine and Wine and Research and development institutions. The session's aim was to highlight the connection between climate information and policy-making processes at different levels and contribute to the discussion on how to make a transition towards more sustainable use of resources or services.

6.4.11. MED-GOLD FINAL SHOWCASE.

The MED-GOLD final showcase event (29 -30 March 2022) had as an objective to disseminate and share end-user success stories from early adopters of the pilot services developed under the MED-GOLD project for Grape/wine, OLives/olive oil and Durum wheat/pasta sectors. A major focus of the event was to provide a hands-on approach to understanding and using the uncertainty associated with climate services.

The first day focused on the success stories from MED-GOLD: what the scientific and our industrial partners gained from being in the project and solving the problems that emerged during the process of co-developing climate services. The second day was dedicated to the contribution of MED-GOLD to society generally speaking, towards a more resilient society but also contributions to the Sustainable Development Goals. The Final Showcase closed with a round table discussion related to the Business Plan and Exploitation. The potential replicability of the MED-GOLD Services was presented through recorded videos during the event.

The numbers provided by the external co-organizer company (*oiko*) demonstrates the acceptance and the work performed during the last 4 years. The summary of the impact are shown below (Table 6-14),

During the event, several sessions sparked the interest of the attendees. This interest is reflected in the numbers of attendees according to each part of the event. Note the increasing number of attendees in the plenaries compared with the number of registered users.

Summary of Dissemination and Communication Activities n.4

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Table 6-15)

Table 6-14 MED-GOLD Final Showcase Participants

Participants	Figure
Accounts Registered	185
Attendees	167
Speakers	46
Exhibitors	26
Active Users	185

During the event, several sessions sparked the interest of the attendees. This interest is reflected in the numbers of attendees according to each part of the event. Note the increasing number of attendees in the plenaries compared with the number of registered users.

Table 6-15 MED-GOLD Final Showcase Attendees

Session	Registered Attendees	Unique Viewers /Attendees	Average Watching
SESSION 1: Co-production: Leading the way in climate services	31	100	1h23min
SESSION 2: Towards useful and usable climate services	28	87	1h05min
SESSION 1: Adopting and using innovation tools in organisations	25	71	53min
Parallel session Room 1: Grape and wine sector		38	
Parallel session Room 2: Olive and olive oil sector		19	
Parallel session Room 3: Durum wheat sector		12	
Parallel session Room 4: Coffee and other agri-food sectors		13	
SESSION 2: Talking Climate for Policymaking	24	63	44min
SESSION 3: The legacy of MEDGOLD: the European landscape and beyond	19	56	1h04min
SESSION 4: MED-GOLD Road To Business (format roundtable)	41	37	

The interaction between the MED-GOLD partners and the participants are part of the impact produced by the final event (Table 6-16). A sample of this interaction is the recently article published article in the magazine [Olive Oil Times](#)

Table 6-16 MED-GOLD Final Showcase Networking and Usage

Network	Figure
Contacts Made	70
Total Messages Exchanged	338
Total Discussions Created	49
Clicks on MED-GOLD advertisement banner	27

Figure 6-19: MED-GOLD Final Showcase in Media

6.4.12. SUMMARY OF THE REPORTED PERIOD

The main results of the reported period are presented in a qualitative way according to the impact measured through the website and social media analyses. The website had an increasing trend (based on the number of views), where the multilanguage content and the consolidated design (fronted) played a relevant role to the publication of dissemination material like infosheet and newsletter. In addition, although the goal proposed (2000 users) has not been reached yet, the social media channel increased the number of users, impressions and engagements compared to the previous reported periods.

The alternative ways to website as a mean of communications were the social media, YouTube channel and external communication channels (Twitter, LinkedIn, websites, radio, TV, etc), which enhanced interest in the MED-GOLD project.

The intensive work performed since the second General Assembly (Oct-2019), and the capacity to perform dissemination work like the Living Lab have been key to reach good results.

Some of the numbers reached during the third reporting period are summarized in Table 6.8

Table 6-17 MED-GOLD Activity results from Nov 2020 - May 2022

Activity	Measure
MED-GOLD WEBSITE	
Website Users	11528
Number website Sessions	15951
Number Page Views	32199
Bounce Rate	66.52%
Average Session Duration	1:42
Number of sessions per user	1.38
Pages/Session	2.02
MED-GOLD SOCIAL NETWORKS	
Followers	522
Number Twitter impressions	137393

Activity	Measure
Number Twitter engagements	3348
Number Twitter retweets	675
Number Twitter likes	893
Number Twitter media views	1631
Number Twitter URL clicks	404
Twitter engagement	536
YouTube Channel Videos	38
YouTube Channel Visualisations	2869
MED-GOLD MAILING LISTS	
Contacts increasing rate	66%
Number of Academic Network	35
MED-GOLD NEWSLETTERS	
Total number of published Newsletter	7
Newsletter Published this reported period	3
MED-GOLD EVENTS	
Conferences participations (12 online)	
Conference Oral presentations	10
Poster	2
Organized events	
Participatory Workshops	8
Webinars	2
Living Lab	1
Final Showcase	1
MED-GOLD Final Showcase (attendees)	167
Discover how to apply the MED-GOLD climate services to different sectors (attendees)	71
Coproduction of climate services: success stories from MED-GOLD (attendees)	87
MED-GOLD Living Lab 2021 (attendees)	16
Participatory Workshops (Active participants)	98
INTERACTION WITH OTHER INITIATIVES	
New Interactions	11
EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION CHANNELS	
Accumulated External media channel contribution (partners)	135
Accumulated Publication in news external websites contribution	36
DISSEMINATION CHANNELS	
MED-GOLD Living Lab	1
MED-GOLD Infosheet (6 language)	5 (30)
MED-GOLD Webinar	2
New MED-GOLD Forum Opened Discussions	0
MED-GOLD Infographic (6 language)	6 (36)
MED-GOLD Publications	
Papers in this period/cumulated papers	14/20
Cumulated Abstracts Submitted	23

Activity	Measure
CONTACT WITH THE POLICY COMMUNITY	
Promotional Videos	4
Participation in International Initiatives	5
Policy Brief	1
ZENODO	
Files associated to MED-GOLD	37
Views on Datasets	395
Views on Documents	815
Downloads (data)	472
Downloads (docs)	680
GLOSSARY and Translation Activities	
Keywords	30
Languages	6
Translation Activities Requested	17

During the Final showcase MED-GOLD in Numbers was presented, which collected some of the results achieved up to this date.

RESULTS

Figure 6-20: MED-GOLD in Numbers

7. EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS

All activities and outcomes described in the previous chapters can be used in the frame of the tasks of WP5 and WP6 mainly, but not exclusively; dissemination and communication imply necessary support of other MED-GOLD work packages too.

The results presented constitute the most representative and effective way to consolidate the strategies adopted during the period (M37-M54) to engage public referred to a different set of users than stakeholders (academic, scientific community, sectors where MED-GOLD is potentially replicable, etc.) to participate in the MED-GOLD project. In the same way this document can be used under the criteria of open data accessible to the general public.

8. APPENDIX 1 KPI'S

The following KPI were collected from the latest review report (31 May 2020). Some metrics will differ from those showed in Table 6-17 which correspond to the period (1 Nov 2020 to 31 May 2022)

Type of activity	KPI						
Website	Number of visits: Total sessions 18707 01/06/20 -31/05/21 Sessions: 7227 Users: 4786 Session/user: 1.51 Page/session: 2.18 01/06/21 -31/05/22 Sessions: 11547 Users: 8504 Session/user: 1.36 Page/session: 2	Country distribution (%) Italy: 15% USA: 10% Spain: 8% Portugal: 4.5% Greece: 4% France: 3% Hong Kong: 3% UK: 2.5% Netherlands: 2.5%	Time spent 01:49	Number of downloads of documents available: Indirect measure:	Observations Special issue with Indonesia: 22%.		
Social networks - twitter	Number of average tweets per week Total Tweets: 302 01/06/20 -31/05/21 182 3.5 Tweets/week 01/06/21 -31/05/22 120 2.3 Tweets/week	Number of followers (2000-3000 users) Total Users 522 New users: 130	Number of impressions per month Total Impressions 165312 6888 Imp/month	Number of visits per month Engagement 3882 161 engagement/month	Likes 1009	Retweets 747	
MED-GOLD community database	Number of registers (500 stakeholders members)	Type of organization registered (company, public agency, administration, academia, large scale producers, small farmers, SME (%)) Academic Institution: 6.4% Consulting: 1.5% Cooperative / Association: 1.3% Distributor of Agrarian product: 0.2% Farmer: 1.1% Large Scale Producers: 8.3% Local Administration: 0.2% Policy : 0.9% Public Administration: 3.4% Public Institution: 1.1%	Distribution of organizations per sector (%) Academic: 7.5% Agriculture: 21.3% Communication: 0.6% Environment: 0.4% Industry: 9.2% industry - Agri-Food: 21.3% Industry - Technology: 2.8% Other: 1.5% Policy: 5.3% Science - Climate: 7.9% Science R+D+I: 19.0% Services: 3.2%				

		Seller and Distributor: 3.8%					
Newsletters, factsheets, news, report, press release	Number of newsletter Total 7 Newsletter (6 Languages) 01/06/20 -31/05/21 2/year 01/06/21 -31/05/22 2/ year	Number of press or news release 01/06/20 -01/06/22 18 News released	Number of journalistic articles 01/06/20 - 01/06/22 14 Published papers	Number of other contributions 01/06/20 - 01/06/22 5 Infosheets 6 Infographic (6 Languages)	Type of media 01/06/20 - 01/06/22 4 Promo Videos (6 language subtitles) 38 Videos in Youtube Channel 2868 Visualisations		
Training – Technical materials 5 User Guide	Number of publications 01/06/20 -01/06/22 20 linked in MED-GOLD website 23 Abstracts Submitted 36 appearances in External media Interview (EN): 3 Press release (EN): 5 About MED-GOLD (IT): 7 Interview (IT): 2 Podcast (IT): 1 Video (IT): 1 About MED-GOLD (ES): 7 Video (ES): 1 News (ES): 1 About MED-GOLD (PT): 7 Press release (PT): 1	Number of downloads or impressions 01/06/20 -01/06/22 1016 views in multilanguage pages /media/: 638 /it/media-it/: 179 /es/media-3/: 105 /pt/media-2/: 64 /fr/media-fr/: 30 Number Twitter media views: 1631	Observations: The user guide are part of the infographic narrative.				
Event participation	Number of events participated (<i>10 international conferences</i>) 12 Conferences 2 Exhibitions	Distribution of international, national, regional or local events (%) Online (12)	Number of posters exposed 2 poster	Number of presentations performed 10 Presentations	Type of event (fair, scientific conference, technical exhibition, industrial meeting, etc.) Scientific: 3 Climate Conference: 4 Expert Group: 3		

Workshops (event organization)	Number of workshops organized	Number of attendees	Gender distribution (%)	Country distribution (%)			
	11 Events 7 Participatory Workshops 1 Living Lab 2 Webinar 1 Final Showcase	MED-GOLD Final Showcase (attendees): 167 Discover how to apply the MED-GOLD climate services to different sectors (attendees): 71 Coproduction of climate services: success stories from MED-GOLD (attendees): 87 MED-GOLD Living Lab 2021 (attendees): 16 Participatory Workshops (attendees): 98	Female: 37% Male: 61% N/R: 2%	Armenia: 0.21% Belgium: 0.21% Denmark: 0.21% Deutschland: 0.21% Israel: 0.21% Luxembourg: 0.21% Romania: 0.21% Slovakia: 0.21% Taiwan: 0.21% Turkey: 0.21% Uruguay: 0.21% Albania: 0.43% Cyprus: 0.43% United States: 0.43% Australia: 0.64% Tunisia: 0.64% Colombia: 0.85% Germany: 0.85% Lebanon: 0.85% Canada: 1.07% Brazil: 1.28% France: 1.49% United Kingdom: 3.41% Greece: 14.07% Spain: 17.06% Portugal: 21.11% Italy: 32.62%			
Scientific publications	Number of publications (<i>10 scientific papers</i>) Total published paper: 20	Impact factor of the publications Views on website: /documents-publications/: 974 /es/documents-publications/: 116 /documents-publications-2/: 66 /fr/documents-publications-2/: 60	Observations This is an indirect measure collected from views in the MED-GOLD website. No guarantee the visit on the host of each paper.				

END OF DOCUMENT

